

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

UDC: 630.2:004.45

FEATURES OF FORESTRY INSTITUTIONS IN A MARKET ECONOMY

Abayeva K.,
Toktassynova F.,
Amanbayeva E.,
Shynybekov M.,
Oraykhanova Ai.

Kazakh National Agrarian Research University,
Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418261>

Abstract

The following categories of forest protection are defined in the Shaldai forestry institution, general condition; protective forest belt along the highways of republican and regional significance steppe forests, pine forests (occupies 94% of the total area of the forestry). The protective categories of forests for the Beskaragai forestry institution are as follows, republican and protective forest belt along the highways of regional significance slopes of a pine forest.

Keywords: forestry, institution, total area, burned area, protective forest belt, clearing, renewal, reconstruction, logging, landscape, forests.

Introduction: Due to the construction of fire-fighting ditches, woodlands will be reduced by 3%. 732 hectares of the area covered by forest will be transferred to block projects. The total area covered by forest will increase by 11336 hectares. And the area of pine plantations will increase by 11205 hectares. Due to the construction of rearguards, birch fields will be reduced by 3 hectares, grasshoppers by 12 hectares. Due to the construction of fire-fighting ravines, the area of aspens will be reduced by 14 hectares, and also due to artificial cultivation of fires will grow by 160 hectares. Due to planting of plantings (19871 ha), as well as their natural cultivation (911 ha), the area of fires will be reduced by 20782 ha. Due to planting (393 ha) and natural cultivation (276 ha), the area of cuttings is reduced by 669 ha. During the reporting period, forest reproduction was established on an area of 75083 hectares not covered by forest, on an area of 24008 hectares [1]. Within ten years, the forest management provides for planting of planting forests on an area of 50704 hectares on an area of 20280 hectares (the annual area of planting of planting forests according to the forest reserve adopted by the forest management is 2028 hectares). The implementation of measures established by forest management improves the ecological condition of forests [2]. The area covered by forest will increase, and the average reserves of plantings will increase by 526.8 thousand m³. Consider the dynamics and level of indicators characterizing potential and real volumes of timber harvesting, which are the basis of forest management. The use of wood resources is carried out on the basis of logging of primary and intermediate use, logging in reforestation, as well as repair, restoration logging, landscape logging [3].

The main territory of the forest fund consists of such tree species as pine (99.0%), aspen (61.4%), birch (14.5%), and elm (14.4%). Most of the territory (631 hectares) is filled with shrubs. The peculiarity of the

age composition of forests is the predominance of young trees and middle-aged plantings [4]. An important place in the complex of measures aimed at the formation of sustainable, highly productive and valuable plantings, the preservation and strengthening of their protective, water-saving, sanitary and hygienic and other useful functions is assigned to logging for maintenance purposes. The purpose of the lighting works is to adjust the composition and frequency control on mixed young rods, in cleaning-the content of the composition and shape of plantings, in thinning-maintaining the shape of the trunk and lethargy to improve the quality and structure of plantings, in transitional cutting-propagation of shoots on selected trees, while improving the quality of technically mature wood care of plantings in order to reducing the time of its cultivation and preparation of plantings for the main logging. When supporting logging during the intermediate operation, a significant amount of commercial wood is produced [5].

Analysis of the volumes of logging for maintenance purposes established by the forest management showed that logging in Shaldai (40% for the liquid fund) and Beskaragai (35.5% for the liquid fund) institutions was performed only by 37.9%, which indicates partial fulfillment of the volumes of logging for maintenance purposes provided for by the previous forest management for the reserve [6].

Research results: in order to preserve and restore pine strips that perform important conservation functions and have special ecological, scientific, cultural and recreational value, the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan adopted a resolution "on the transfer of especially valuable woodlands to the category of forest protection" (February 19, 2001 No. 254), and in November 2002 -on when they were transferred to the state forest nature reserve, they were transferred to the reservation.

The adopted resolution on the organization of natural reserves on pine strips will allow preserving and restoring landscape and biological diversity, to ensure balanced use and sustainable development of natural resources of these territories. The average areas of the forester's plot, the forest viewing zone are shown in Table 1 of the regional forestry departments for the Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve.

As can be seen from the table, the Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve was created from Shaldai and Beskaragai forestry institutions, the Shaldai institution occupies an area of 143247 hectares (51.5% of the total area by SNNP), and the Beskaragai institution occupies an area of 134714 hectares (48.5%). The Shaldai institution is divided into 9 forest districts, and Beskaragai - into 7 forest districts. The most profitable volume of forestry for the region is an institution with 8-10 forestry areas of 50-80 thousand rubles.

Table- 1.

Administrative and economic structure of the Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve according to

Forestry	Total area, ha	Forest master's plot		Forest viewing zone	
		number, units	average area, ha	number, units	average area, ha
The Shaldai forestry					
Galkin	12109	2	6010	9	1345
Bauyrtal	14977	2	7488	11	1362
Stepnoy	16476	2	8238	11	1499
Seyten	15640	2	7820	11	1422
Sadikashchi	18571	3	6190	12	1548
Shoshkaly	13353	2	6676	10	1335
Shaldai	19550	3	6517	13	1504
Zavodty	14715	2	7358	11	1338
Pervomay	17856	3	5952	12	1488
Total by forestry	143247	21	-	100	-
Forestry average	15916	-	6916	-	1426
The Beskragai forestry					
Maikaragay	19785	3	6595	14	1413
Taybagar	17206	2	8603	11	1564
Bayimbet	18315	2	9158	13	1409
Beskaragai	20933	3	6978	14	1495
Kokterek	16881	2	8440	12	1407
Kokzhal	24572	3	8191	17	1445
Maraldy	17022	2	8511	12	1418
Total by forestry	134714	17	-	93	-
Forestry average	19245	-	8068	-	1450
Total by SNNP	277961	38	-	193	-
SNNP average	17373	-	7420	-	1437

Accounting of the forest fund is conducted according to district, stock and other taxation indicators. This in itself allows for a comparative analysis of the structure of the forest fund for several years. According to the calculations of the forest fund of the Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve, of January 1, 2005, the total area of the forest area of the Reserve was 225985 hectares or occupies 81.3% of the total area (Table 2).

Table-2.

Distribution of the total area of the forest fund by land categories information of January 1, 2005

Valley name	Total area by SNNP Yertis Ormany		District by institutions of the State Forest Nature Reserve			
			Shaldai		Beskaragai	
	ra	%	ra	%	ra	%
1. Total area of the Reserve	277961	100	143247	100	134714	100
2. Total forest area	225985	81.3	116879	81.5	109106	80.9
2.1 Forest-covered lands	148298	53.4	80482	56.2	67816	50.3
Including forest trees	28367	10.2	15933	11.1	12434	9.2
2.2 Uncollected trees	2106	0.8	1025	0.7	1081	0.8
2.3. Forest nurseries	98	0.03	31	0.02	67	0.05
2.4 Lands not covered by forest, total	75483	27.1	35341	24.6	40142	29.8
Including burned areas	51560	18.5	27618	19.3	23942	17.8
Places where trees were felled	1576	0.6	342	0.2	1234	0.9
Fields	21946	7.9	7376	5.1	14570	10.8
Rare forests	401	0.1	5	-	396	0.3
3. Forest-free valley	51976	18.7	26368	18.4	25608	19.0
Including torn areas	731	0.3	356	0.2	375	0.3
Grasslands	22515	8.1	12479	8.7	10036	7.4
Pastures	17073	6.1	7696	5.4	9377	7.0
Waters	532	0.2	211	0.2	321	0.2
Roads, quarter lanes	4452	1.6	2411	1.7	2041	1.5
Localities	620	0.2	383	0.3	237	0.2
Swamps	427	0.2	214	0.1	213	0.2
Sands	15	0.01	13	0.01	2	-
Other valleys	5611	2.02	2605	1.8	3006	2.2

As can be seen from Table 2, according to the natural reserve, the treeless valley makes up 18.7% of the total area of the reserve. 8.1% of the deforested area is occupied by meadows, 6.1%-pastures, 1.6%-roads, quarter strips and 2.02%-other lands. Most of the burned lands fall on the Shaldai forestry institution and account for 19.3% of the total area of the institution. In Beskaragai forestry institution, 17.8% of the total area of the institution was burned, 10.8% of the area, 0.9% of deforestation, 0.3% of rare forests.

In the forest area we can observe the following changes: over 10 years, the area of the forest reserve has decreased by 37192 hectares. Of these, 23021 hectares (22.0% of the total area covered by forest) were reduced in the Shaldai forestry institution and 14171 hectares (17.3%) in the Beskaragai forestry institution. The main reason is high forest fires in a vast area. The area of plantings on burnt trees was 10637 hectares.

The area of plantings without tree joints decreased by 2.4 times due to a decrease in the volume of tree planting. If during the reporting period 10 years ago, 18965 hectares were planted in Shaldai and Beskaragai forestry institutions, then only 9414 hectares were sown during the reporting period from 1991 to 2005. The age composition of the forest fund reflects the area of the forest that can be used now and in the future within the age groups (Table 3).

As can be seen from the table, on the territory of the reserve coniferous trees occupy 94.8% of the area covered by forest, and deciduous trees – 5.1%. The Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve is filled with middle-aged plantings (occupies 66% of the total area covered by forest). Of these, coniferous forests make up 97%, deciduous-2.9%. Among young plantings, the share of Class II plantings prevails and for the reporting period amounted to 18.9% of the area covered by the forest.

Table 3.

Distribution of the area covered by the forest by age groups and types of trees

Types of tree	Forest-covered area, ha							
	total	including by age groups					the beginning of growing up and dried up	
		Age group in Grade I	Age group in Grade II	average age group	the beginning of growing up	total	including dried up	
Pine	140687	6094	27788	95037	8823	2945	41	
Cedar	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	
Coniferous trees, total	140688	6094	27788	95038	8823	2945	41	
Maple	70	1	3	67	-	-	-	
Violets	1100	-	21	1077	2	-	-	
Birch	1108	63	22	952	71	-	-	
Blue Poplar	4674	2360	266	552	903	593	-	
Poplar	15	-	-	3	5	7	-	
Other types of tree	12	-	-	2	5	5	-	
Bushes	631	1	19	211	153	246	243	
Deciduous trees, total	7610	2425	331	2864	1139	851	243	
In total	148298	8519	28119	97902	9962	3796	284	

Over the past 6 years, logging for maintenance purposes has not been carried out at all in the forest reserve. As a result, high-altitude plantings, in which no supporting logging was carried out, under the influence of natural destruction turned into dumps. And this, in turn, leads to the death of wood, a decrease in sanitary conditions, an increase in fire hazard. According to the accounting of the forest fund for the past forest management, 44354 hectares of old-age trees were registered in the forest reserve (including unassembled forests of forests), including 26384 hectares in the Shaldai forestry institution, 17970 hectares in Beskaragai. During the registration period, 17,167 hectares (38.7%) died as a result of the fire. The state of the preserved

forest fund was assessed in accordance with the "technical instructions of the procedure for assessing and accounting for the quality of forest management plantings". Forest stands moved in accordance with these instructions to the territory covered by forest have the following characteristics:

- fullness 0.8-1.0
- good, fullness 0.6-0.7
- satisfactory, fullness 0.4-0.5
- unsatisfactory.

In old-age forest stands, with a fullness of trees 0.4-0.5 is 41%.

Let's consider the structure and dynamics of expenditures on public administration and forestry by reserve (Table 4).

Table - 4.

Dynamics of the structure of costs for forestry and forest weapons according to the Yertis Ormany Nature Reserve, (thousand tenge)

Name of indicators	Years				
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Costs-total, including:	64269.0	101193.7	278378.8	208429	297860.0
On reforestation	24948.0	18869.8	26570.5	49197	89691
On protection of forests from fires	7856.0	25034.3	59404.8	72601.1	92176.4
Other expenses	31465	57289.6	192403.5	86630.9	115992.6
Percentage of forest management costs, %					
Costs-total, including:	100	100	100	100	100
On reforestation	38.8	18.6	9.5	23.6	30.1
On protection of forests from fires	12.2	24.7	21.3	34.8	30.9
Other expenses	49.0	56.6	69.1	41.5	38.9

In the dynamics of the structure of operating expenses for 2018-2022, it is possible to observe an increase in the costs of reforestation and fire prevention measures. Reason: increased production costs associated with the inclusion of forest protection costs in the costs of fire prevention measures.

Conclusion: There are 1,373 fires registered on the territory of the forest reserve, covering an area of a total of 40,580 hectares. According to the forest management conducted in 2019, the fire area was 51100 hectares. The area of forest fires in the Shaldai institution was 1.8%, the number of fires was 1.2%. The average fire area was 30 hectares. And in the Beskaragai institution, the fire area was 29 hectares, 648 fires were registered. In the period from April to November 2005, due to large forest fires that covered 820 hectares in the Shaldai institution and 795 hectares in the Beskaragai institution, the forested area decreased. The main cause of forest fires are anthropogenic factors. 36% of forest fires were caused by thunderstorms. Forest fires often occur during agricultural work, as well as as a result of improper use of fire in forests by local residents.

References:

1. Forest Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. - Almaty: Jurist, 2004. - 66 P.
2. Yanushko A.D. Economy of the forest economy. - Minsk, 2004. - 368 P.
3. Pochinkov S. V. Market model of forest management: economic aspects //forest management. – 2000. No. 1. - pp. 26-29.
4. Baizakov S. B., Mukanov B. M. Problems of sustainable management of forests and forest management in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2007. - 96 P.
5. Koval I. A. System of state management of the forest management at the modern stage // Forest and forest management in the market: problems and prospects for sustainable development. International scientific and practical conference. - Almaty, 2003. - Book 2 - 175 P.
6. Ormanbayev O. Forests of Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 1971. - 144 P.